

RSB: Reflexive Systems Biology – Towards an Appreciation of
Biological, Scientific and Ethical Complexity

Funded by the Research Council of Norway (FUGE)

**Policy Report:
On Integrated ELSA Methods**

December 3, 2013

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The work leading to this report was funded by the Research Council of Norway, Project 187969/S10.

On integrated ELSA methods.

Background and Summary

(by Roger Strand, RSB Project Leader)

The final deliverable foreseen by the project plan of the 3-year project *Reflexive Systems Biology* is a “policy report”, prepared by us as an input to the policies of the Research Council of Norway on the requirement of *integrated ELSA*. The report builds upon the experience accumulated throughout the RSB project (as well as our previous experience).

This report coincides with another report by Norwegian ELSA researchers (including myself) to the Research Council on the lessons learnt from the two ELSA programmes (ELSA 1 and ELSA 2). The topic of this report is a different and supplementary one. The present report does not evaluate the identity and need of ELSA *per se*. It is a contribution to the ongoing research and policy discussion about what *integrated ELSA* is, could be and should be. Its intended audience include the ELSA secretariat of the RCN and also the secretariats and possibly programme boards of large programmes such as BIOTEK2021 and NANO2021. It might also be useful for the ELSA research community itself. In this way, the RSB project wished to communicate back to our funders in an intellectually more satisfying manner than the usual final report.

The report is prepared by the RSB postdoctoral fellow Ana Delgado, with only a minor edit by myself. I support her conclusions, though. Although the report is rich in reflections and descriptions of practical experience, I would like to highlight three issues:

The need to tailor integrated ELSA. While some authors have proposed (one might even say *marketed*) standard “methods” for integrated ELSA, Delgado presents arguments and evidence for why integrated ELSA is more meaningful if tailored according to the context and concerns of the research group that is the subject of ELSA integration. This is the case for **content** of the ELS aspects to be addressed, but also the **form and method** by which they are addressed.

The documentation of best practices. Rather than a standard, mechanical “method”, we offer a set of descriptions of best practices, tailored to three different contexts. The value of these descriptions does not lie in that the approaches can be blindly copied, but rather in seeing how the understanding of the context and concerns of the natural scientists has been translated into the integrated ELSA approach. This approach, which is a methodological novelty of the RSB project, Delgado has called an **ethnography of living things**.

The question of voluntary vs mandatory integrated ELSA. Without taking sides in this ongoing policy issue, the report analyses how integrated ELSA research is confronted with different challenges if the ELSA integration was externally required as opposed to being chosen by the natural scientists themselves. The report expresses a concern for the quality of the ELSA interaction when ELSA is forced upon the natural scientists, in particular if there is a “free ELSA market”, that is, natural scientists are required to include ELSA, but they are free to choose who and what. As this is the present arrangement in BIOTEK2021 and NANO2021, I would encourage the secretariats of these two programmes to study this report.

Introduction: Integrated ELSA methods

In the context of responsible research and innovation, the need for “integrated ELSA” methods is often justified on the basis that ethical, legal and social aspects of research must be disclosed, discussed and integrated in the research process at an early state. This “upstream” integration shall enable to shape the future of emerging technologies in more desirable (Frow and Calvert, 2013) and responsible ways. A key idea is that by acting “up” and “midstream”, a desired impact “downstream” will be achieved. Integrated ELSA research is then expected to trigger ‘reflection’ within the scientific community, hence facilitating the emergence of new forms of responsibility, and therefore a *better science*. The relation between reflexivity, responsibility and better science is nevertheless not one of causal necessity. This is, they do not lead one to the other in a mechanical and linear fashion. Still, reflexivity is a condition of possibility for responsibility, which is also, from our point of view, a necessary condition for enabling *better science*. In real situations of “integrated ELSA research”, nevertheless, it is difficult to assess if and how new forms of responsibility have indeed resulted from the integrated research processes. This is, among other things, because in most cases both reflexivity and responsibility do not appear as immediate and obvious results. Rather they may manifest within long-term processes and they may emerge in non-expected forms, in midterm or long term futures (e.g. scientists starting some kind of initiative). The ELSA approach developed within the RSB project, therefore, assumed reflexivity as a condition for future forms of responsibility to emerge.

Disclosing "innovative things" in system and synthetic biology; STS meets researchers in the lab.

Working with scientists in systems and synthetic biology laboratories

As central part, RSB project included the use of ‘integrated ELSA’ methods and approach to facilitate, more reflexive and ethically grounded developments in systems and synthetic biology. Such work was carried out from September 2010 up to November 2012 in three different institutions: Centre for Genomic Regulation (Barcelona-Spain), The Biodesign Institute (Arizona State University-USA) and the Institut Canilles de Biodiversitat i Biologia Evolutiva (Valencia-Spain). To perform our “integrated ELSA” research, we developed a methodological approach that we called “ethnographies of innovative things”. This approach is inspired in STS previous laboratory studies (Latour and Woolgar, 1979 Knorr-Cetina, 1999, Rheinberger,1997) but tries to bring them into a more normative and ‘integrated’ approach.

The research preceding this work in the labs was of a theoretical kind and included a review of the scientific literature on systems and synthetic biology as developed in the natural sciences, STS and ELSA fields. This preliminary research led us to the conclusion that neither systems nor synthetic biology is one. Rather a multiplicity of approaches, research strategies, types of applications, intellectual property right regimes and research values, among other elements are at

play within the emergence of both systems and synthetic biology. Hence, adding to their scientific complexity, empirical complexity becomes noticeable when one looks closely to these emerging knowledge fields. Indeed, ‘systems’ and ‘synthetic’ biology has been used as umbrella-terms that cover a multiplicity of disciplines, often although not necessarily pointing to new interdisciplinary relations. As an effect of such multiplicity, it is also difficult to establish *a priori* which is the relation between systems and synthetic biology. The actual shape that that relation may take remains an empirical question. As we have argued “The border between these two fields is not always easy to draw: sometimes systems biology is understood as providing valuable theoretical basis for synthetic biology and some- times theory is understood to be a hindrance to the advance of synthetic biology (Delgado, Funtowicz and Dankel, 2012:12). In engineering approaches to synthetic biology the emphasis is on making “things” that work to satisfy desired functions, while the production of theoretical knowledge is seen as a byproduct of the research activity (Schwyter, 2013). However, the production of advance theoretical knowledge is the goal of some branches of systems biology. Differences in “techno-epistemic cultures” (Kastenhofer, 2013) translate into further crucial issues of an ethical and sociological kind. For instance, while some scientists may take biological complexity very seriously, others argue that the best way of dealing with complexity is by “getting rid of it”. This diversity leads to further methodological, social and ethical differences, for instance regarding which are the adequate standards and safety measures to be taken and what kind intellectual property rights forms are the best (see below). In the RSB project, we embraced diversity as a constitutive element within the emergence of systems and synthetic biology. Hence, instead of trying to reduce heterogeneity, we decided to include it as a crucial element of our methodological approach. ‘Contextually’ has therefore been a main pillar of our research. For instance, when we approached the different laboratories where we work, we started by situating the research groups within specific scientific traditions. Indeed, it is common that the “systems” and “synthetic” biology label has been adopted only quite recently, and so these scientists have in most cases ‘double identities’ such as developmental biologists/systems biologists or molecular biologists/synthetic biologists. Different backgrounds correspond with different ways of understanding, accepting and adopting of ELSA approaches (see also below).

Why looking at “innovative things”?

In spite of the diversity presented above, systems and synthetic biology are emerging fields that belong within a common policy and historical moment; they belong within a certain technoscientific culture. Particularly in Europe, science and technology policies seem to have moved the focus from the development generic enabling of technologies to the existence of a number of societal “grand challenges” that need to be address. This move is fundamental to understand European innovation policies in which applications that directly address such challenges are likely to be prioritized. Hence, technoscientific research is directed to specific “contexts of application” (Carrier and Nordmann, 2011)

As emerging knowledge fields, both systems and synthetic biology projects are assessed and warranted on the basis of to their relevance in terms of innovation. Within this context, it can be argued that even basic research is increasingly expected to produce *something*. As for instance, the research work that we worked with in Barcelona was specialized in developmental biology with

an aim to produce basic knowledge on the developmental process of the *Drosophila* fly. In a sense this was very classic research, scientists were developing models to understand and explain such developments. Still they were expected to produce a ‘software application’ that could possibly be used in other contexts, and their research was ultimately justified in terms of its possible medical applications.

Attending to similarities in terms of justifications and the general orientation in research policies and practices, we decided that our integrated research approach would focus on the products of scientific research. The strategy then, would be to discuss and disclose such products together with their producers, the scientists. In our work with scientists we focused on the “innovative things” that they were producing in their labs. By using a diversity of methodological paths, we encourage scientists to ‘open-up’ the black boxes of science. The focus on particular applications, and how they were made, allowed for discussions on choices, values, property rights, among other things.

An ethnography of innovative things?

The reason why we called our research methods “ethnographies of innovative things” is because we intended to use the ‘interpretative distance’ that characterizes the ethnographic method, but we wanted to share it with the scientists so that there was not only one allowed interpreter. The ‘right to interpret’ would be shared by many. In a sense, we intended to turn scientists into ELSI researchers, making them the subject and object of participant observation. We thought of this as genuine reflexive turn at the core of our methodological approach. Like in classic ethnographic studies, we expected that by taking an ‘interpretative distance’ towards the things they produce, scientists would be able to disclose the meanings, imaginaries and values involved in the making of such things.

To facilitate ‘reflexivity’ at a collective and not only at an individual level, we alternated periods of observation and individual talks in the lab together with a number of ‘dialogic sessions’ (3-4 group sessions in each laboratory). The particular themes of discussion in each of such sessions was not pre-selected by us but it came about out of participant observation-time in the labs and the informal talks in which scientists expressed issues of concern. For instance, ‘Intellectual property rights’ emerged as a prominent theme; scientists were generally concerned with what may happen to the things they were developing. Another issue of concern was how to communicate their science to the general public as to gain public acceptance. During the dialogic sessions, we encouraged scientists to imagine their ‘role’ not only as scientists but also as citizens and humans (in terms of responsibilities and in relation to both society and nature). As mentioned above, we pushed them to take on distant and interpretative positions about their own work. Inspired by Marcus (1995), we used the notion of the technoscientific imaginary in order to facilitate such interpretative work. Even when we did not impose themes and views, we tried to facilitate their emergence and in this sense, the ‘integrated’ research process was inevitably guided to some extent. We encouraged scientists to situate the things they produce in three time-dimensions: 1) In the past, in connection to particular research traditions and backgrounds; 2) Present: the methods and disciplinary approaches at used in the labs; 3) Future: focusing on the issue of how would the applications they are developing ‘work’ out of the lab if

succeeded (implications and benefits for society). In this way, we got to situate the products of their research and to project them in time, opening up for discussion on concrete issues. Furthermore, we tried to stimulate the scientists to connect such particularities with broader issues related to the nature of life and the possibility of fabricating it. To stimulate and trigger discussion, we used different strategies. For instance, we played the role of the “skeptical” and the “stranger”, making obvious, annoying and sometimes even absurd questions (e.g. are genes alive?).

In this section we have presented some general features of our methodology. However, we changed and adapted our way of proceeding each time, in accordance to the particularities of the context where we were working. For instance, in the systems biology laboratory where we worked in Barcelona, the production of images is central, the scientific work relying on a prominent culture of visualizations (see below). Accordingly, our research focused on discussing and disclosing such imagery. In contrast, in the Valencia lab, we worked with undergrad students that were developing a project for iGEM, an international competition that awards cool, playful and exciting projects. Consequently, we promoted that the students could use and turn ELSA into an ‘exciting’ element of their project. Eventually they made a movie with our support as supervisors. The process of making the movie was a way to facilitate reflexivity on the particular application that they were developing. The next section describes how we performed ELSA research in different ways, in three different laboratories.

Multiple things and sites and multiple ways of developing “integrated methodologies”

On models and visualisations: Centre for Genetic Regulation/Barcelona

The Centre for Genomic Regulation in Barcelona is an institution funded by the Spanish Ministry of Innovation in collaboration with a number of private enterprises. The research structure includes a systems biology section. This division is made up of four research groups, one of them named: “Comparative Analysis of Developmental Systems”. Johannes Jaeger is the leader of this group of ten members, most of them young post-docs¹.

¹http://pasteur.crg.es/portal/page/portal/Internet/02_Research/01_Programmes/06_Systems_Biology/06_CompAnalysisDevSystems

Figure 1: Centre for Genomic Regulation, Barcelona

From September 2010 to April 2011, we performed a number of visits to this lab. For a period of about 15 days, we were given a workspace in the lab so that we could stay together with the members of the group learning about what they did in their everyday working life and interacting with them. Besides, 3 dialogic discussions of around 2 hours each were carried out. In addition, interviews with all members of this group were conducted, recorded, transcribed and analyzed. Furthermore, we organized a 2 days workshop on systems biology in Bergen and we invited two members of this lab (the leader and one of the post-docs). A result of this workshop was 2 manuscripts co-authored by members of the RSB consortium and those two members of the Jaeger lab (still work in progress).

In my first visit to this lab, the leader organized a group session to introduce their work. Broadly, the researchers in this group share a concern with how living systems develop and new forms and shapes appear in evolution. Their project pursues comparative knowledge on the processes of development (body segmentation) of two flies (*Drosophila* and *Clogmia*). Through the use of advance digital pictures, they identify development patters, looking at the gene regulatory networks that compose the thorax of these flies. Such patterns are then turned into the object of modelling activities in a continued feedback and adjustment between *in silico* and wetlab experimenting. While part of the researches in the group is trained as “experimental biologists”, others have a background in bioinformatics.

Figure 2: Imagery produced/use at the Jaeger lab

In our early informal talks in the lab, we started to learn about the scientists' individual work and we asked about the potential ethical and social implications of their research. Two researchers identified some issues related to the legal aspects (PR) of software development and also expressed preoccupation with how synthetic biology is increasingly oriented towards specific contexts of application. However, a more repeated message among lab members was that what they produce is basic theoretical knowledge and so, if the models and software that they produce should be used for any other applied purpose or application, that is not their concern. A common view, thus, was that there are not ethical nor social issues directly involved in what they do. In view of this first reaction, we organized a first dialogic session on the open topic: "Are there ethical and social aspects related to systems biology research?". The way in which we proceeded here was by inviting the researchers to envision their research in contexts different from the lab (policy, legal, public). The debate ended up revolving around four issues: 1) Reactions against funding being increasingly allocated to applied science, in particular systems biology applied approaches; 2) The ethics of research (defending "basic research values" such as "curiosity" against "applied research ethics"); 3) The commoditization of knowledge; 4) A need to become better at communicating with the public (as 'entrepreneur scientists such as Craig Venter do), and to get involved in educating the public.

Figure 3: Hair ball network used in proteomics approaches

Following the scientists' reactions and concern that "what they do is basic science", we proposed a discussion around the nature of the knowledge that they produce, as the topic for the next dialogic session. As these scientists expressed a feeling of being somewhat threatened by applied forms of doing biology and specifically systems biology, we decided to start the session by presenting one of the graphics produced by their 'enemies' (Figure 3) to provoke the discussion. Some 'kick off' questions were 'what does the image represent', 'is this a model' 'a model of what?' Such simple questions triggered a cascade of reactions of the kind 'this graphic just *pretends* to represent reality, but it provides no insights', 'this graphic gives a false representation of complexity to convince/impress policy-makers and the public', 'this is not a real model'. Hence, the discussion turned towards what a real model may be. We then confronted the scientists with images produced in other labs as well as the imagery of their own modelling activities (Figure 2). We asked them to trace back and reconstruct the history of the models and equations that they use, as well as their model organisms (*drosophila* and *clogmia*). In addition, we confronted them with the equations and algorithms behind such models, and asked how they would address complexity. This triggered an interesting confrontation between the member of the group that is in charge to develop the experiments *in silico* (modelling) and the member of the groups that is leading the wetlab experimenting. They accused each other of 'assuming too much' and 'taking a lot for granted' in their work. This opened for further discussion on what is 'taken for granted' and how reality is simplified and the complexity of living organisms dismissed when making models. Questions on what complexity is, and how it can be represented or misrepresented (in the form of networks) and on the possibility of predicting the developments of living systems became central to the discussion. As this was a very vivid discussion, we decided to organized a third session with a 'broad' focus on 'what life is' and the 'possibility of fabricating' it. This would be the third and last group session. Briefly, here the discussion revolved around the issue of to

what extent biology works as physics. Life was defined as an emerging property (someone even said “a miracle”). The possibility of fabricating life (as in synthetic biology) was not denied, yet the need to proceed ‘slowly’ was emphasized on the argument that more basic knowledge is needed. Thus, a sort of ‘weak’ precautionary approach could be identified within this discussion.

Vaccines: Biodesign Institute/ ASU

The second site of our integrated research was the Biodesign Institute at Arizona State University. Particularly we worked with scientists at the Centre for Infectious Diseases and Vaccinology². More concretely, we worked with scientists that were developing a recombinant vaccine to fight pneumonia in developing Countries. This was a long-term project that received funding from the Bill and Melissa Gates Foundation. In this site we were allowed to be in the lab performing participant observation for a period of ten days. Informal talks and in-depth interviews were combined (a total of 7 recorded and transcribed interviews). Furthermore we organized and invited the scientists to participate in 4 dialogic sessions. Biographical interviews with the leader of the Centre were used to situate this project.

Figure 4: Biodesign Institute ASU

The group of scientists that we worked with in this lab is designing recombinant vaccine. The purpose is to make a pneumonia vaccine that is more efficient. The strategy is to use salmonella bacteria as a vehicle. Salmonella has the capacity to enter and spread in the human immune system very quickly. In this project the novel idea is to re-design and use that capacity for the ‘good’ purpose of “tricking the immune system” (quoting one of the scientists) to produce antibodies quickly. The design of the vaccine proceeds by reducing the salmonella genome,

² <http://www.biodesign.asu.edu/research/research-centers/infectious-diseases-and-vaccinology>

knocking out genetic parts that produce infection while conserving the ‘infective’ capacity of salmonella. Salmonella is to be designed as a vehicle, a chassis. To the extent that the project has a strong focus on design, it can be defined as a synthetic biology project that takes on a ‘minimal genome’ approach (Delgado *et al.*, 2013).

In our early conversations with the scientists in this lab, we adopted the role of the ‘naïve public’, asking obvious question of the kind: ‘how is it possible that a bad bug is turned into a good bug and how safe is that indeed?’ The question came from the observation that, as scientists pointed out when describing their work, the biggest effort along the years has gone to “attenuate” the infectious capacities (pathogenic) of salmonella without eradicating its potentials. We focused on this work of ‘attenuation’ and tried to disclose and problematize it in conversations with the scientists. As ‘attenuation’ by design was a main focus of activity, for these scientists main issues of concern related to the salmonella vaccine were control and biosafety. Indeed, the project was to design a vaccine that should include ‘biocontainment’ measures so if things go wrong, the entire device would de-activate itself. We confronted the scientists with the questions of how genetic engineering could possibly be used to control the risks it creates. Further issues related to biosafety were discussed during the dialogic sessions; for instance, issues related to how such a vaccine would actually create safety in developing countries. It turns out that such countries have often more relaxed safety laws, so it is possible to introduce the vaccines at an earlier stage of research and with less testing than in northern countries where regulations are more strict. A further argument was that in these countries where diseases spread very fast people are willing to adopt vaccination even if vaccines did not go through so many safety tests. Discussions revolved around these kind of ethical problems. In addition, during the dialogic sessions we encouraged discussions on how scientists relate to nature in what they actually ‘do’ in their everyday activities in the lab. The new salmonella type produced in the lab was seen as modified nature. Further questions on how this modified bug could possibly affect the normal course of evolution if released in the environment came about. Beyond safety issues, the scientists in this group, and specially the leader, were highly concerned about intellectual property rights issues. On the basis that they understood what they do as a substantial improvement on nature and a service/good for society, patents were the preferred IP form.

Living things: switches and talking bacteria/ iGEM Valencia

From May 2011 until November 2012, we worked with two groups of undergraduated students in Valencia (Spain). They were mainly biotech and engineering students at the University of Valencia and the Polytechnic University of Valencia. In our work we focused on two projects developed in 2010 and 2012. These projects had been developed in the framework of the iGEM Competition. iGEM stands for International Genetically Engineered Machines. It is an international competition in which hundreds of teams from all around the world compete to develop the best synthetic biology project during a short period of 3 to 4 months. In the frame of the competition, the students are trained in synthetic biology, particularly, on the strand of synthetic biology known as bioengineering (Desplazes, 2009). As a requirement of the competition, the teams need to develop at least one “BioBrick” (a minimal DNA functional part). These BioBricks are open source biological entities. Stored in an open online repository, the Registry of Standard Biological Parts, BioBricks are accessible to the community of synthetic

biologists. They are seen as basic pieces to be assembled into more complex biological devices and systems (Delgado, submitted). Hence, the BioBricks are understood to be the first step towards a composable kind of biology in which the complexity of the biological systems is a result of assembling.

Figure 5: iGEM project 1 (<http://2010.igem.org/Team:Valencia>)

In Valencia, we followed and researched two projects. The first project (figure 5), called Mad Yeast on Mars consisted in the development of a prionic switch that was envisioned as a central element in a possible process of “Terraforming Mars” (<http://2010.igem.org/Team:Valencia>). As envisioned by the Valencia Team, this biological switch would be a first step to regulate the temperature on Mars to resemble Earth conditions. The project had been developed for the 2010 competition. We addressed it retrospectively by performing a number of interviews with the students in which they remembered and reflect of the project. Furthermore, we organized three dialogical sessions where issues specifically related with the project and broader issues related to the possibility of fabricating life were addressed. The most remarkable feature of these group talks was the disagreement between biological and engineering views on the possibility of designing living systems *de novo*. To further disclose and systematically explore such disagreements, one of us co-authored a paper with one of the supervisors of the team (Delgado and Porcar 2013).

Figure 6: iGEM project 2 (http://2012.igem.org/Team:Valencia_Biocampus)

For the 2012 project (Figure 6), we were asked to participate as ‘instructors’ in the Valencia Biocampus team. It is mandatory for iGEM projects to include a section on “Human Practices” that addresses the ethical and social aspects of the project. Our role in the project was to give advice, design and develop this part of the project with the students. In the context of the iGEM competition, projects that are visionary, innovative, creative and cool are prioritized. We thought, our ‘Human Practice’ collaboration should be adapted to the general framing of iGEM.

From the first ‘brainstorming meeting’ we were invited to participate in the design of the project. The project was called “Talking life” and the idea was to develop a biological based device that would enable communication (<http://2010.igem.org/Team:Valencia>). The application of this device would be a sensor mechanism that would be used to monitor people with memory problems (such as senile people or people with Alzheimer) at a distance, particularly to control that they take their medicines in the right time and doses. The application of the device was envisioned and chosen in one of our first ‘Human Practices’ meetings. Furthermore, from May to October 2012 the students worked in developing a methodology for the ‘Human Practices’ section of the project that would enable discussion on the ‘talking life’ device that they were developing in the lab. We were available online and working with the students on an every-day basis. Furthermore, during that summer one of us travelled to Valencia for two weeks to work intensively with them. In an early meeting it was decided that the students would produce a movie that would serve as a vehicle to communicate and discuss their project with the public (this was suggested by us and enthusiastically accepted by the students)³. The process of making

³ The idea of using a movie as vehicle to trigger ethical discussion was suggested by us. This methodology had been used before in a previous project at SVT (See <http://technolife.no/>). The method that the students in Valencia developed was inspired by the Technolife methodology yet brought a step further: As the students took the role of

the movie opened up for discussions on the nature and potential ethical and social problems related to the project. The movie ended up focusing on issues of biosafety and biosecurity, such as biohacking and the risk of possible biological mutations. In making the movie the students followed a number of steps: First they did a search and a scoping exercise in which they identified the main issues of concern related to their project. Second, they selected some main themes and they translated it into a movie script; Third, they shot the movie. During the shooting they had to create the situations (scenery) and play the different roles they had created in their script; Fourth, they planned and carried out a number of public debates. The movie was subsequently shown in different locations and with diverse audiences (In civic centres and in science cafes as well as in academic settings and in different European countries such as Spain, France and Norway). The students planned and guided the public debates as well as they recorded, analysed and reflected on those debates. They reported on the steps they followed in their “Human Practices” methodology in their website: http://2012.igem.org/Team:Valencia_Biocampus/Ethics. The movie is available on YouTube: <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PW4o7-V7KeY>.

As reported in the website, the students managed to make a terrific amount of work. The methodology that they used was designed to favour discussion and reflexivity. For instance, the students developed their movie in collaboration with a film company. The process of negotiating with the film company (i.e. how to turn their ideas into movie language) was particularly interesting and provided good room for reflection. The movie makers were constantly asking and questioning the students’ choices (they would ask questions such as: ‘why do you really want to talk about biohacking?’, ‘do you want it to appear as a good or a bad thing?’, this is unclear in your script’). Potentially, this constant questioning could have triggered rich internal reflections. However, the team kept referring to issues of biosafety and biosecurity in rather narrow and stereotypic ways, and reflections did not get to develop as far as we would have liked to. The reason for this, we think, was to a large extent imposed by the context. Working in the context of the iGEM competition, the students were pushed to develop their project fast and in a way that would be appealing to a jury. We believe, nevertheless, that the methodology that we developed in collaboration with the students in Valencia has a good potential for integrated ELSA, particularly for those projects that aim at facilitating room for reflexivity such as RSB.

What’s the value of an “integrated ELSA”?

The question that gives title to this section is one that we repeatedly had to face when working with scientists in an ‘integrated’ mode. In none of the three institutions where we worked was it immediately obvious to scientists what the value and function of ELSI research was and how it would benefit and enhance their research and scientific production. To different degrees, we always needed to justify our work. This was not always easy, not the least because scientists would often use scientific criteria of productivity to assess the value of ELSA. Not surprisingly,

movie makers, the movie became a vehicle for internal reflection as well as a way to trigger ethical debates with further audiences.

when assessed from that perspective, ELSA has no obvious value. Furthermore, not unusually, ELSA is understood by scientists as a sort of an ‘outreach’ or ‘science communication’ activity that can serve to enhance public acceptance of scientific activities. For instance, in the Biodesign Institute at ASU scientists became keen on collaborating with us on the expectation that the result of such work would be a publication in a high-ranked scientific journal. They also expected that such a publication would serve to facilitate the public acceptance of their recombinant vaccine. They were encouraged by the fact that one of us had co-authored a commentary in the journal *Nature*. Trying to move beyond normal criteria of scientific productivity, it was generally difficult for us to make the point that ELSA is actually ‘research’ and that it has a value in itself. Issues that for us appear as obvious, as the value of ELSA to produce a more ‘socially robust’ and ‘reflexive’ kind of knowledge were difficult to explain in a way that would make sense for the scientists.

In the course of the RSB project we got in touch with other ELSA researchers in other countries where they have been facing similar problems. Noticeable, in the UK a workshop was organized by the ELSA community on these issues in the Kings College in July 2012. A number of leading ELSA researchers invited representatives of the synthetic biology community to discuss what they called a ‘Post-ELSI Manifesto’. The Manifesto addressed the role and value of ELSA research. One of the researchers of RSB was invited to comment of this manifesto⁴. This gave us the opportunity to witness the reactions of the synthetic biology representatives in the room, some of them strongly reacting to accept that ELSA is indeed of any value to their scientific production. As a result of such reaction, the manifesto had to be withdrawn from the Internet and reformulated. **This is, indeed, a quite exhausting side of being an ELSA researcher, the amount of time that you need to use in justifying yourself and convincing others.**

For what we have experienced, nevertheless, such politics of justification work differently depending on whether one works in a context where ELSA is mandatory or voluntary. For instance, at the CRG in Barcelona we introduced our ELSA project and we openly invited all research groups in the institution to take part. The leader of the institution questioned the value of our project quite heavily and most research groups did not consider our invitation. Only the leader of one of the research groups thought that RSB might be interesting and somewhat enlightening. The result of that kind of genuine curiosity was a type of collaboration that was indeed quite interesting and of a high quality, from our point of view. Participants questioned their work and discussed assumptions and issues that are generally taken for granted. In the context of the iGEM competition, however, an ELSA component is mandatory. In the previous section, we provided a brief description of our work with the Valencia Biocampus team. The team was really eager to have us as instructors, nonetheless because this would increase their chances of winning the competition. We tried to adapt our work to the iGEM frame, hence making ELSA easy, cool and fun, but in a sense also rather superficial. A problem imposed by the context was that the students were too focused on winning the competition and this made real reflection difficult. As a mandatory component, ELSA acquired in this context a rather instrumental value. In this setting we were most satisfied with the work we got to develop with one of the advisors of the team out of the context of the competition. In the course of our collaboration, he developed a genuine interest in ELSA, particularly reflecting on the kind of

⁴<http://www.kcl.ac.uk/sspp/departments/sshm/research/csynbi/ProgrammeSocialScientistsAdventuresSB.pdf>

‘living things’ that synthetic biology is producing (See Delgado and Porcar, 2013). Our impression is nevertheless, that scientists who express interest in ELSA are seen by others in the scientific community as doing ‘soft’ work rather than ‘real’ productive scientific work.

In view of these diverse experiences, we have been wondering whether it would be better to claim ELSA as a mandatory or a voluntary component of systems and synthetic biology research. On the one hand, making ELSA voluntary would probably doom it to be always in a threatened position, ELSA researchers always needing to justify their work. On the other, making it mandatory would probably be a move towards its instrumentalization and a decrease on quality. Our main concern is that if ELSA becomes mandatory, a ‘free market’ would emerge in which scientists call ELSA researchers to participate in their projects on the basis of scientific criteria of productivity rather than on the basis of robustness, reflexivity and quality. If ELSA is to become mandatory, such a market should be ‘regulated’. This means that collaborations will have to follow criteria that are not imposed by natural scientists alone. **Perhaps national research councils and ethics panels should have an important role in regulating ELSA collaborations.**

Finally, an important element of the ELSA ‘politics of justification’ as presented so far is that, many times it is not even clear for us, members of the ELSA community what the value of ELSA is and what our role as ELSA researchers should consist of. In the turn from ‘ELSI research’ to ‘integrated ELSA’ (see also the recent (2013) expert report on ELSA submitted to the Research Council of Norway), a number of questions need to be opened for serious debate within the ELSA community. To our mind, some key questions are: ‘what should the concrete outcome of integrated collaborations be? And related to this, what kind of knowledge do we produce when we work with scientists in integrated ways? For whom is this work relevant? In which way is ELSA ‘research’? how can it actually contribute to ‘better’ scientific research? A serious debate on the nature and politics of ELSA research is still needed.

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